

Moroccan Jews and Muslims Discussing Online Their Mutual Heritage: The Moderation Role of Nostalgia on Well-Being and Social Network Participation

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ABSTRACT

Increasingly, users of social networks engage in multicultural discussions involving nostalgia for a shared past.

The current study continues the exploration of the impact of nostalgia and social network participation among Moroccan Jewish and Muslim online community users dealing with their cultural heritage. The relationship between nostalgia and well-being has been extensively discussed, but as far as we know, there is little research exploring nostalgia as a moderator of social network discussions. In the current study, we hypothesize that mood at nostalgic moments moderates the dealing with Morocco and multicultural communities from June 2019 to February 2020. Four questionnaires were used in the study: demographics, social network participation, nostalgia mood, and well-being. As a result, 96 Jews and Muslims born in Morocco answered the questionnaires. Our results confirm that nostalgia contributed significantly to the well-being and that among participants with a high level of nostalgia, a higher level of well-being contributes to a higher level of social network participation. These findings are important as a positive effect of the contribution to social networks could lead to a higher time spent on social networks, which should be investigated in further research. This article's dataset will be published in an online repository.

KEYWORDS

Nostalgia, social network participation, well-being, Morocco, Jews, Muslims, online diaspora, digital cultural heritage.

INTRODUCTION

The idea for this research came in 2018 while observing the many online nostalgia groups on Facebook and wondering why Moroccan Jews and Muslims born in Morocco wrote nostalgic posts about their shared heritage, some institutionalized (Mimouna.com, 2021) and others based on personal initiatives. These groups declared three objectives: promoting and disseminating the mutual history shared by these religious communities, renewing cultural and friendship ties, and advocating Morocco. These nostalgia groups grew fast, discussions were respectful and not combative, and personal participation was encouraged. A search of similar online diaspora revealed that these groups were unique among multicultural social networks. Members of Facebook nostalgia groups about Morocco wrote about nostalgia, though they did not always use this term. Instead, they shared recipes, pictures, movies, events, and customs that triggered nostalgic discussions.

A previous exploratory study (Ouaknine & Aharony, 2020) that analyzed the posts in these groups resulted in four main themes: nostalgia expressed in online posts; social network participation that is considered a primary objective of the online community; nostalgia landscapes represented by childhood or city memories, and well-being related to past or present situations. In the current study, we thrive on understanding how nostalgia and individuals' present well-being may increase social network participation.

RELATED WORK

The religious communities of Morocco

Morocco is a monarchy in North Africa, distinguished by its Berber, Arab, Jewish, French, Spanish, and Portuguese influences. The country was established in 780 AD and now has a population of over 36 million. Three groups emigrated from Morocco in the 1950s (Miller, 2010) and today form a significant diaspora.

The first group comprised 4.5 million Moroccan Muslim natives who chose to live abroad, mainly in Europe and for economic reasons (Boukharouaa et al., 2014). The second group to emigrate was the Jewish community, numbering 250,000 in the early Sixties. Currently, only 1% of this community still resides in Morocco; the majority left for Israel, France, Canada, the United States, and many other destinations (Zafrani, 2005). The third group was mainly composed of French expatriates who left Morocco after independence in 1956. Other national groups are those who speak Tamazight (Berberic) or Spanish. All the religious groups use French and Moroccan Arabic, known as "Darija," as their primary language. Ritter (2017) considers Moroccans who left their country as a "Diaspora" with similar roots, practices, or languages. He also argues that the Moroccan diaspora abroad expresses the need to fill a cultural and religious gap and renew lost traditions. This gap is filled by social network participation in discussions, as individuals talk about the cultural memorabilia of Morocco, customs, and folkloric artifacts and exchange practical information (Ritter, 2017).

WELL-BEING, NOSTALGIA, AND SOCIAL NETWORK PARTICIPATION

Well-being is a psychological concept that expresses feelings linked to other emotions, such as life satisfaction and loneliness, and has been widely explored (Diener, 2009). This approach, known as the "hedonic tradition," focuses on life satisfaction and positive, high, and low adverse well-being effects (Dodge et al., 2012). In contrast, other researchers (Dodge et al., 2012) propose a new definition of well-being that features an equilibrium between the individual's psychological, physical, and social resources and the challenges to face. According to this definition, the psychological, physical, and social challenges and resources are imbalanced when resources need to support a challenge. In other words, following Davis' (1977) argument, people who feel that their present well-being is seriously deficient may use their psychological, physical, and social resources to cope with it (Dodge et al., 2012), and nostalgia may be one of those resources.

Research presented a solid and positive relationship between social network participation in social networks and well-being for four primary needs: socialization, entertainment, self-status seeking, and information (Park et al., 2009). Aharony (2015) found that well-being and attitudes towards social networks and intention to use them increase users' social capital in a study that examined the antecedents of WhatsApp participation, a mobile messaging service for smartphones. In addition, recent research confirms that routine use of social networks is associated with positive health outcomes, but excessive social media use is associated with adverse health outcomes (Bekalu et al., 2019).

METHODOLOGY

Problem Statement

The current study explores the impact of nostalgia and social network participation among online community users dealing with their cultural heritage. Different studies considered the following topics: nostalgia in offline settings (Davis, 1977; Sedikides et al., 2018), participation in social networks (Aharony, 2015; Douglis, 2010), and well-being (Diener, 2009). The relationship between nostalgia and well-being has been extensively discussed, but, as far as we know, there is little research exploring nostalgia as a moderator of social network discussions (Davalos et al., 2015; Hepper et al., 2020). Furthermore, investigations of multicultural and inter-religious communities discussing their shared past in social networks appear scarce (Illman & Sjö, 2015), especially among Moroccan Jews and Muslims. In the current study, we hypothesize that mood at nostalgic moments moderates the relationship between well-being and Social network participation.

Analysis

The research was conducted in Facebook groups dealing with Morocco and multicultural communities from June to February 2020. An invitation was sent to 41 Facebook groups to participate in the study. Three major themes were expressed in the information parts of the Facebook pages.

1. Multicultural relations between Muslim, Jewish, and Christian communities (N = 20).
2. The cultural heritage of Morocco, including pictures, old movies, architecture or cooking (N = 16).
3. 5 Facebook groups featured Morocco as an attractive destination. The list of Facebook groups can be found here: <https://bit.ly/2IPCOZV>.

Four questionnaires were used to gather data: The demographics section included religious community and place of birth; The social network participation questionnaire was employed to measure different underlying constructs and consisted of five statements rated on a five-point Lickert scale (1=strongly disagree; 5=strongly agree) and was adapted from research conducted by Ongena, van de Wijngaert, and Huizer (2013) about the relation between nostalgia proneness and behavioral intention to share a cultural heritage in online communities; The nostalgia mood questionnaire was based mainly on Davis' (1977), Routledge et al. (2008), and Ongena et al. (2013) work on nostalgia and The well-being questionnaire "well-being assessment and satisfaction of life" scale (Diener, 2009). The full questionnaire is available here: <https://bit.ly/3ZFiuZg>. Participants could leave the questionnaire at any time and the participation was voluntary.

A two-tailed independent samples t-test and a two-tailed Mann-Whitney two-sample rank-sum test were conducted to examine whether the mean mood at the nostalgic moment was significantly different between Moroccan Muslims and Jews born in Morocco. In addition, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted for five variables of well-being and Social network participation, using parallel analysis to determine the number of factors to retain with varimax rotation. Finally, we hypothesize that (H0) Mood at a nostalgic moment does moderate the relationship between well-being and social network participation. All the analyses were performed with the Intellectus statistics software (Intellectus Statistics [Online computer software], 2022).

Results

96 participants answered the survey, 49 Muslims and 47 Jews. Among the Muslims participants, 69% were men, 61% graduates, 67% married, and 47 years old (SD=14). Among the Jewish participants, 62% were men, 51% graduates, 72% married, and 65 years old (SD=10).

Participants were asked about their mood before a nostalgic moment . The result of the two-tailed Mann-Whitney *U* test was not significant based on an alpha value of .05, $U = 1230.5$, $z = -0.61$, $p = .544$. The mean rank for Muslims was 50.11 ($M=3.73$, $SD=1.06$), and the mean rank for Jews was 46.82 ($M=3.64$, $SD=0.97$). This finding suggests that the mood distribution at nostalgic moments for Muslims ($Mdn = 4.00$) was not significantly different from the mood at nostalgic moments for Jews ($Mdn = 4.00$).

Well-being construct

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted for five variables of well-being using parallel analysis to determine the number of factors to retain with varimax rotation. The well-being construct accounted for 63.03% of the variance, with an eigenvalue of 3.15. In addition, the items for well-being had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .84, indicating good reliability.

Table 5 indicates that participants most of the participants noted high scores for their satisfaction with life (item 1 - I am satisfied with my life, item 3- I have gotten the important things I want in my life, and item 4- The conditions of my life are excellent) and relatively low scores for item 2- My life is ideal, and item 5- I would change almost nothing if I could live my life again. These findings are similar to the values indicated by Kobau [35]. In addition, the items for well-being had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .84, indicating good reliability.

Social network participation construct

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted for five variables of social network participation using parallel analysis with varimax rotation. The Social network participation construct accounted for 66.06% of the variance, with an eigenvalue of 3.30. In addition, the items for Social network participation had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .90, indicating excellent reliability.

Variable	Factor loading	Communality
The creation of internet groups of Moroccan Jews and Muslims should be encouraged	0.83	0.69
These groups of Moroccan Jews and Muslims on the Internet help preserve Moroccan memory	0.88	0.77
I will participate in these groups more than other groups on the Internet	0.79	0.62
It is easy to post photos and videos on online groups	0.68	0.47
I would recommend my friends to participate in these groups on the Internet	0.87	0.75

Table 1. Factor loadings of the social network participation construct

The items for Social network participation had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .90, indicating excellent reliability.

Moderation analysis

Moderation analysis was conducted to assess if the mood at a nostalgic moment moderated the relationship between well-being and Social network participation. Mean centering was used for well-being and mood at the nostalgic moment. In the first step, a simple effects model was created using linear regression with Social network participation as the outcome variable and well-being as the predictor variable. In the second step, a non-interaction model was created by adding mood at a nostalgic moment to the predictor in the linear model in step 1 (simple effects model). In the third step, an interaction model was created by adding the interaction between well-being and mood at a nostalgic moment to the predictors in the linear model in step 2 (non-interaction model). Finally, assumptions for linear regression analysis were conducted for the step 3 model (interaction model).

For moderation to be supported, two conditions must be met (Netemeyer et al., 2001). First, the causal predictor variable, well-being, must significantly predict Social network participation in the simple effects model (step 1). Secondly, the interaction model (step 3) must explain significantly more variance in Social network participation than the non-interaction model (step 2). If either of these conditions fails, moderation is not supported. These regressions will be examined based on an alpha of .05. well-being significantly predicted Social network participation, $B = 0.26$, $t(91) = 2.52$, $p = .014$. Therefore, the first condition was met, and the second condition was checked. A partial F-test was conducted to determine if the interaction model explained more variance in Social network participation than the non-interaction model. The partial F-test, $F(1,89) = 7.72$, $p = .007$, indicated that the interaction model significantly explained more variance than the non-interaction model, based on an alpha of .05. Therefore, the second condition was met. Since well-being significantly predicted Social network participation in the simple effects model (condition 1) and the interaction model explained significantly more variance of Social network participation than the non-interaction model (condition 2), moderation is supported.

Table 2 presents a comparison of the non-interaction and interaction models. The mood at nostalgic moments significantly moderated the effect well-being had on Social network participation based on an alpha of .05, $B = 0.27$, $t(89) = 2.78$, $p = .007$. This finding indicates that, on average, a one-unit increase in the mood at a nostalgic moment will cause a 0.27 increase in the slope of Social network participation in well-being.

Model	R^2	F	df	p
Non-Interaction	0.09			
Interaction	0.16	7.72	1	.007

Table 2. Linear model comparison table between the non-interaction and interaction model

The mood at the nostalgic moment was dichotomized into high and Low categories using a median split to visualize the moderation analysis. The High category indicates all observations of mood at the nostalgic moment above the median, and the Low category specifies all observations of mood at the nostalgic moment below the median. Figure 1 shows the regression lines for Social network participation predicted by well-being for the High and Low mood categories at the nostalgic moment.

Figure 1. Regression lines for social network participation predicted by well-being for the high and low categories of mood at the nostalgic moment

Simple slope analysis was used for the mood at a nostalgic moment to analyze any significant moderation in the model based on an alpha of .05. Mood at the nostalgic moment was examined at one standard deviation below the mean (2.66, low level), at the mean (3.68, medium level), and at one standard deviation above the mean (4.69, high level). With a low mood at the nostalgic moment, the slope of well-being on Social network participation was not significant, with a value of -0.005, $p = .974$. However, with a medium mood at the nostalgic moment, the slope of well-being on Social network participation was significant with a value of 0.27, $p = .014$. Finally, with a high mood at the nostalgic moment, the slope of well-being on Social network participation was significant with a value of 0.54, $p < .001$. This finding suggests that mood at nostalgic moments increases in value, and the slope of well-being on Social network participation also increases.

DISCUSSION

This article focused on nostalgia, well-being, and social network participation. Considering the lack of research on nostalgia and social networks, we suggest that nostalgia moderates the present well-being, increasing social network participation in dealing with a shared past.

Our results confirm a positive correlation between well-being and social network participation and the interaction between nostalgia and social network participation. This research is novel, as the role of nostalgia in social network participation was relatively unknown. Previous research (Davis, 1977; Newman et al., 2019; Routledge, 2016; Sedikides et al., 2018; Wildschut et al., 2006) suggests that there are mixed effects (positive and negative) of nostalgia on well-being, but little is known about the correlation between nostalgia, well-being, and social network participation.

Our key findings show that nostalgia contributed significantly to the well-being and that among participants with a high level of nostalgia, a higher level of well-being contributes to a higher level of social network participation. Our analysis also suggests that, in addition to the positive effects of nostalgia, social network participation positively correlates with individual well-being among the main Moroccan religious groups. These findings may conclude that nostalgic content in an online discussion may increase the social network participation of users. These findings are important as a positive effect of the contribution to social networks could lead to a higher time spent on social networks, which should be investigated in further research.

There are several limitations to the study. The first is that we included only participants that were born in Morocco. The second relates to the fact that the questionnaire was in French. Although French is a widely spoken language in Morocco, the survey should be published in other languages spoken in the country. A third limitation is that the questionnaires were filled in 2019-2020, which implies the need to compare the results after the covid-19 pandemic. Nevertheless, these findings show why further research should investigate qualitatively and quantitatively the Moroccan diaspora's central themes in an online discussion, in fields related to nostalgia, like genealogy, religious sites, artifacts, traditions, food, and roots tourism, but also to time spent in social network activities. Finally, further research should define how nostalgia and mutual heritage in social media may become "social media for good"

DATA

This article's dataset is available in the Mendeley Data repository: <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/3vx6knxg3t> doi: 10.17632/3vx6knxg3t.1

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